

Barriers and facilitators of components of the integrated care service						
√ = Network 7 facilitator; ✓ Network 9 facilitator; x = Network 7 barrier; x = Network 9 barrier						
CFIR domain	Component of the community specialist team					
	Working as a team	Managing referrals	Conducting HCP education	Conducting patient education	Conducting patient appointments	Monitoring the service
Characteristics of the service components						
Trialability of Excel data collection						✓
Complexity of initial data collection instrument (Excel) design						x
Relative advantage of co-location to meet patient needs	✓✓				✓✓	
Relative advantage of 1:1 education to focus on patient needs				✓		
Internal context and setting of the service						
Resources						
Systems						
Self-populating (HealthLink)	✓	✓				
Lack of risk screening prompt (HealthLink)		x				
Lack of caseload management (Diamond)	x					
Diamond batch function to generate appointment letters					✓	
Lack of automatic function to generate reports						✓✓
Lack of function to book joint appointments	x					
Shared physical space	✓✓			✓✓		
Staff/time						
Lack of admin resources	x x	x		x		x x
Available, dedicated time within network/project			✓			✓
Hospital foot protection team sees active foot						✓
Limited podiatry and CNS staff		x				x
Lack of mental health services to meet patient needs		x				
Waiting list for physiotherapy services		x				
Waiting list for vascular services		x				
Waiting list for hospital appointments		x				
Networking & leadership						
Ease of networking	✓, ✓	✓				✓✓
Team triage	✓					✓

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Relationships with PHNs for cover		✓					
Team members being 'out and about' at clinics/practices	x x						
Direct referral to vascular services		✓					
No colleagues within discipline to 'bounce things off'					x		
Leadership from project management team	✓				✓		✓
Lack of local leadership (overarching manager)	x						
Knowledge/training							
Community & hospital system interoperability	✓						
Lack of Diamond & HealthLink interoperability		x					
Access to colleagues' notes via shared IT system	✓						
No access to information on patient hospital visits		x					
Unable to access a computer in general practice		x					
Limited/missing information on referral forms		x					
Access to PHN/PN knowledge via education				✓			
Lack of footcare screening education (dietitian)		x					
Network boundaries – lack of clarity	x	x x					
(In)compatibility of referrals with criteria		x x					
External environment and context							
Guidance/policy							
Footcare guidelines 'not realistic'					x		
ICGP guidelines on foot screening 'difficult to enforce'		x					
Patient needs and resources							
Patient lack understanding of reason for CNS appointment					x		
Nursing home and homebound patients not seen by podiatry		x					
Cost of private practitioner to address patient needs (nail cutting)		x					
Characteristics and attitudes of practice staff and clinicians							
Lack of IT skills (Excel)							x
Implementation process							
Engagement							

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Engaging & building 'rapport' with practice staff	✓	✓✓	✓			✓	
Consultant champion to bring consultants on board	✓						
Challenge engaging patients in online DESMOND				x			
Planning	✓						
Planning the service (workflows, referrals) as a team							
Team triage to reflect and generate solutions	✓						
Monitoring							
Compatibility/ incompatibility with existing statistics/KPIs							✓✓ x
Some data points not captured/accessible							x
COVID-19							
Engaging HCPs due to COVID-19			x				
Cancelled clinics – no physical exam						x x	
Mix of F2F, online, and phone appointments -accessibility						✓	
Acceptance of inappropriate referrals – GP insufficient time to educate		x					

Healthlink provides a web-based messaging service which enables the secure transmission of clinical patient information between Hospitals, Health Care Agencies and General Practitioners <https://www.ehealthireland.ie/a2i-hids-programme/healthlink/>

DIAMOND is a computerized diabetic clinic management system